

Rhythms of Resistance: Intersectional Feminism in Maya Angelou's Poetic Voice

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Abstract

The present paper explores the theory of Intersectional Feminism in select poems of Maya Angelou. Most of her work is on her actual experiences and hardships as a black woman. Feminism, in general, is considered as the only idea in which women should be equal to men, but it is not true to its core. Its more conducive branch called Intersectional Feminism presents the understanding of how women faced racism, religion and the impacts of abuses and discriminations. Intersectional feminism has come from the term intersectionality which means, the acknowledgment that everybody has their own experience of discrimination and oppression such as sexism, homophobia, transphobia and many more. Therefore, it represents a type of feminism that makes us aware of this system and the condition of female in society. Maya Angelou in her poems talks about freedom, challenges restrictive notions of feminine beauty and about self-respect and confidence. She says that she will rise to any occasion; nothing can hold her back. This paper will talk about the aspects of feminism through this noted African-American poet.

Keywords: Intersectional Feminism, Marginalisation, Oppression, Self-confidence, Self-determination, Traumatic Experience, Unconditional Love, Healing

Maya Angelou was born on April 4, 1928 in St. Louis Missouri, U.S. died on May 28, 2014, in Winston-Salem, North Carolina. She was a well-known black American activist, writer, dancer, and poet. One of the most expressive and inspiring literary voices from American literature who used to express herself in a very strong manner. Maya Angelou used to live with her grandmother as a child. She was raped by her mother's boyfriend, for which he was sent to jail, and after being discharged, he was murdered. This brutal experience left her in trauma, and she almost became mute. Interested in writing from a very young age, she wrote essays and poetry, mostly autobiographical. For instance, in *I Know Why The Caged Bird Sings* (1969), she describes her life as she lived with her brother and grandmother, and also about the trauma she faced as a child. After learning the news that the man, her tormentor, has been murdered, she felt responsible thus stopped talking for five years. In *Maya Angelou: The Iconic Self*, Lupton Jane describes the rape as "the ultimate learning experience for Angelou, and that

through her pain she becomes aware of being a small girl in a world controlled by men” (88). In her famous work *Singin' and Swingin' and Gettin' Merry like Christmas* (1976), she tells us about how she began to work as a streetcar conductor and the struggles she faced to get this job. Maya Angelou was just seventeen when she graduated and gave birth to a son, she had multiple jobs to fulfil all the necessary needs of her family. She wrote many such books, essays, poetry, songs, etc, that expresses her views and thoughts about society, struggles and discrimination on her race. In 2010, she was awarded the Presidential Medal of Freedom by President Barack Obama. She was also awarded with over 50 honorary degrees and awards before she died. She also worked on the struggles for civil rights with Dr. Martin Luther King. Maya Angelou's poems have often been the voice for women facing racial discrimination, injustice, and abuse. From talking about these problems so that people became aware and raise their voices, to encourage and give strength to demand social justice, freedom, and determination. To have self-confidence, that outer beauty doesn't matter, it's the inner qualities and characteristics that make one attractive.

During the period of the Atlantic Slave Trade from about 1526 to 1867, millions of men, women and children were captured and voyaged from Africa to America. From the first ship that sailed carrying the first Africans to be enslaved, over the period migration of people carried in slave ships per year increased while reaching new highs. Over a million more were carried out in the slave trade era and were forced to work as slave. A large part of enslaved Africans was brought to British North America between 1720 to 1780. African-Americans were enslaved since the 17th century however, by the time of the American Revolution, which resulted in the adoption of the new constitution in 1787, enslavement was decreasing, and the new constitution decided to end the migration of slaves. However, by 1800, slavery was brought back into the picture. One of the main reasons for this was the origin of widespread acceptance of cotton. To grow these crops, cheap labour where in need, thus making a slave to do all this labour work would be much easier. This would lead to rapid production of cotton with profit. Growing needs of hard and cheap labour, the cotton growers were in the need of labourers to look after the fields, thus slavery of African-Americans spread again. However, the slaves not only worked for the plantation of cotton plants but worked on other agricultural crops such as sugar, tobacco, hemp, corn, rice and indigo. As Angelou describes in her poem *Women Work* (1978) which provides evidence of it,

“The cane to be cut
I gotta clean up this hut
Then see about the sick
And the cotton to pick.” (Line 11-14)

It was not difficult for the rich or those holding power to buy the freedom of the slave. Working in the fields from dawn till after sunset with a break of two hours for a meal was something for the free farmers, the enslaved worked under constant supervision and were threatened to be punished if they lacked in the field work. There was a difference between the two workers, the free farmers were working on their own free will and could control their working time but the enslaved ones did not have such control. This slave trade played a major

role in the development and economic foundation of the U.S, which made fortunes from plantations. The desperation of slavery increased so much that the practice of slave breeding started in which enslaved women were abused and raped from the age ranging from thirteen. They were forced to give birth, and a different form of oppression started to take place. There were laws enforced on them; they were sold like animals, restricted from having a stable family life, no freedom and little privacy. They were not allowed to read, write, and learn; rebelling against these laws would receive brutal punishment. Thus, slaves were unable to bear such tortures and started revolting. They revolt in public by killing white people, damaging property with proper planning, and also revolting individually or try to resist the oppression, such as killing newborn to save them from enslavement, giving poison to the slave owner, destroying crops, and even running away. The free African-Americans and other black communities protested to release the enslaved leading to social movements and revolts. The free black leaders established to aid the black communities. Soon, the leaders started to meet regularly to make strategies to fight against the oppressors. Later, the black leaders pulled themselves out from these movements as they realized that this struggle can only be solved by their own and their native people, as the leaders are American.

The increased slavery formed new territories; soon gaining momentum of social conflicts resulting in the Civil War (1861-1865). It was for the first time that the slaves had power and the whites were frightened. The Civil War happened for the liberation of the black slaves but it did not abolish the slavery system. The expansion of new territories became the point of conflict between the north and south. The announcement to free the enslaved who help to fight in the war, many black people were ready in order to have freedom. The whites did free black slaves and the U.S Constitution made amendments to abolish enslavement. After the end of the civil war, the period focused on rebuilding the enslaved people into the society; empowering the by giving the rights to vote and citizenship; but this amendment was short-lived. After the reconstruction of black slavery abolishment, the southern states again enforced racial exclusion hence, they continued to face discrimination, marginalization, violence, and other forms of oppression. The history of enslavement of black people in America and its prolonged brutality has marked a deep wound on them, be it social, economic, but also psychological, struggles of race, colour and gender persisted.

The Harlem Renaissance came up as a cultural movement that celebrated black art and music. It was in the 1920s that this creative cultural movement took place in Harlem. This movement gave rise to black artists, writers, and musicians. Black did not only rose artistically but also paved the way for their economic conditions. It also gave birth to important black artists and intellectuals who contributed to literature. The divine form of art and literature became a source to vent their agony and struggles of life experience; it also helped to connect and relate to each other, creating a strong bond. It also became a source to freely raise their voice to protest for their rights and freedom, to strike against the oppressor and to resist. The origin of this movement started when the African-Americans migrated from south to north. Harlem was initially for the upper-class white but an increase in the development resulted in the emptying of lands and the want to fill the land, which was later filled by black African-American families which was known as the Great Migration. In the year 1915-16, due to natural

destruction black people had no work. The population of black folk led to the Black Pride Movement which gave rise to a leader named Du Bois who worked for the rights and freedom of the black people. He was a sociologist, activist as well as an author, he wrote several books to describe the black struggle, to bring them justice, he encouraged people unite and raise voices, DuBois says in his autobiography, "There is but one coward on earth, and that is the coward that dare not know."(1940) This gave encouragement for people to share their experiences through words, art, music, and dance. The art and literature during Harlem Renaissance beams light on the different hardships of others, yet providing and motivating hope. The prose, poetry, autobiography and even music also expressed the history of enslavement.

Maya Angelou is one of the most prominent figures in the fields of literature, a writer, a poet, a singer, a composer and even a social activist who had worked alongside Martin Luther in social movements, actively taking a stand for their people fighting for their rights and freedom against the oppressor. Angelou, through her power of words was not only sharing her life struggles but was also motivating others to rise and speak. She speaks of the people who are not just the victims but also the survivors of oppression. She was also a feminist writer who not only wrote in support of women but also worked for their equality. At a very young age, she was raped, and on the complaint against the abuser, he was imprisoned but soon after his release from jail, he was killed. Angelou thought he was killed because she opened her mouth to speak and was terrified to speak again, she was mute for a few years. Her interest in writing started growing during this time. Her financial conditions were also not so good, due to which she had to start working at a very young age of fifteen. As she tried to seek different jobs, she struggled a lot due to her colour and gender. No one was ready to employ a woman who was black. But she was determined. Angelou's first job was as a streetcar conductor. Angelou, even after her graduation, looked for different jobs to meet the daily needs of her family. Angelou, as a feminist writer, encouraged women to stand up and speak for themselves. Her writings are mostly themed about race, gender, and class, exploring the problems in society." Maya reveals the pathetic conditions of the females, whose identity is not established as a human being, hence leading to their state of subjugation by both White and Black males. Maya's poetry also seeks liberation for Black women. In her poems, she seeks to rediscover the history of African-Americans and explore horrible experiences faced by African-American females." (Sunday, N. O., & Ekpo, E. E. 42). Angelou's writings urged black women to seek their rights and freedom, to be treated equally, to protect their individuality and independence, resisting against the oppressor. Angelou's work mostly expressed the view of intersectionality or intersectional feminism to be precise. She believed that black women's life experience is different from white women as she thinks that blacks are doubly marginalized, first as a woman and second as a woman of colour. Being a woman does not mean to only be defined to meet societal norms, to meet oblivious beauty standards, being told what to do and what not to, restricted in doing anything, not allowed to do anything on their own will. Angelou believed that women should have self-confidence, a thirst to protect their independence, self-love, and to speak up for their rights and equality. They should not be subjected to the stereotypes of society. Women should resist such marginalization and other forms of oppression.

Thus, this paper tries to work on revealing the societal oppression on black women in the face of intersectional feminism through the poems written by Maya Angelou. The paper explores the poems of Angelou describing the history of black struggle, freedom, racism, sexism, equality, love, loneliness, etc, in the form of oppression, particularly women while applying the theory of Intersectional Feminism. Many people think that feminism is an idea which only talks of women equality to men but that is not at the core of it. Intersectional Feminism or Intersectionality is described as the interconnected or interrelated nature of social categories such as caste, colour, gender, class, etc. Kimberle Crenshaw coined the term in 1989, the overlapping of such social categories mostly created tensions and social conflicts. It is the understanding of how women faced racism, religion and the impacts of other abuses and discriminations. Intersectional feminism has come from the term intersectionality, which means the acknowledgment that everybody has their own experience of discrimination and oppression such as sexism, homophobia, transphobia and many more. Therefore, it represents a type of feminism that makes us aware of this system and the condition of females in society. Thus her poems are majorly about, "Socio-psychological inferiority, desire for liberation, and anger against marginalization forms the recurring patterns of her poetry." (Ghani and Naz. 96)

The poems by Angelou taken in this paper analyse such social issues by black women sharing their own experiences and other African-American women. How they are enslaved, treated unjustly, snatching their individuality and independence. She believed that women should be self-confident being associated with feminine ideas, beauty, and other such physical attributions they are not confined to these stereotypes. Her poem *Phenomenal Woman* (Angelou, 1978) challenges restrictive notions of feminine beauty. She rejects the idea of societal beauty standards rather insists on real beauty, which comes from self-confidence and self-acceptance. In the poem *Still I Rise* (Angelou, 1978) she talks about self-respect and confidence. She says that she will rise to any occasion nothing can hold her back. In *Caged Bird* (Angelou, 1969) she talks about freedom which is unknown to her. This paper talks about the aspects of feminism through the Black American poet. Intersectionality defines how different discriminatory factors hinder the life of an individual or a whole community, or race, or gender. The addition of intersectionality to feminism created a new movement and a new theory to study. Movement that allows us to fight for gender equality and societal discrimination, and as a study, it allows us to understand it better. While applying it in different works, it gives us a new aspect to read and look at it in a more vivid viewpoint. Maya Angelou is one of the most notable feminist poets. She holds a very powerful literary voice while intellectually addressing issues of intersectionality faced by black women. Her works are themed on racism, sexism, marginalization, and other forms of oppression while encouraging black women to rise and resist. Maya Angelou writes for the empowerment of women who faced abuse and sexual violence, "Maya Angelou's memoir, *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings*, first published in 1969 when she was in her early forties, stands as a powerful testament to the transformative power of resistance and the complexities of being a Black woman in a racist society. Her memoir was one of the first autobiographies by a Black woman to reach a broad audience, offering an unflinching portrayal of her struggles, including racism, trauma, and the search for identity. The memoir is significant not only for its unbiased exploration of these

themes but also for its lyrical prose and the way it weaves together personal and collective histories, making Angelou's experiences universally relatable." (Khayat and Dawla. 12-13) Her writings are deeply rooted with her own struggled experiences. By her poems she braids the black liberation with feminism particularly faced by the women of colour. Black women in the society are doubly marginalized: first as women, they are expected to meet the societal norms and settle in the set structure for women, to bear all the responsibilities and can't do anything on their own will while also not providing equal opportunities, secondly, they are marginalized because of their colour. Angelou gives a fuller picture of various form of oppression, which be it her own experience but still provides the readers a prolonged status of black women in the society. Her poems also manage to the history of enslavement.

In the poem *Caged Bird* (1983), she talks about two birds in which one is flying freely in the open sky and the other is captivated in a cage, which sings for freedom, the birds in this poem are metaphors that are used to symbolise oppression over African- American (blacks) and the privileged (whites). She uses the birds as metaphors to describe the black community's experience of inequality, feminism, racism, and freedom in the United States in particular. The poem explores the opposite experience of the two birds, one who is caged and longs for freedom and the other who is free and gliding in the open blue sky. The poem opens by describing how the bird is free, it can go wherever they want not only they sense freedom but also feels powerful as said in the line "dares to claim the sky." (Angelou, Line 07). The poet further says that the free bird can do everything as it is pleased, but the bird in the cage cannot even look beyond the bar, they can't do anything at their own will. They don't have freedom, which makes them angry and frustrated, "so he opens his throat to sing." (Angelou, Line 14) The poet says that the caged bird sings in a fearful voice, her feet are tied and wings are clipped thus she sings "of things unknown but longed for still." (Angelou, Line 17-18). Here the bird sings of freedom which is never known but still understands it and longs for it. This poem discusses the historical struggles of Black people. How they had limited rights, how they were not treated equally, how they were oppressed." Angelou's poetry is also a liberatory song that releases the silenced voices of African-American people. Hers is the song of a caged bird which is held captive by the prisons of racial bigotry, but the song is also inspiring which proclaims a better, optimistic future. Angelou, however, shows more concern for racist discrimination and injustice than sexist oppression which perhaps emanates from her belief that gender inequity cannot be achieved prior to the demolition of racial inequality which inflicts her entire community" (Guha. 55) The poem highlights the partial treatment between blacks and whites. Angelou's works usually refers to the oppression faced by Black people and how they were subjected to physical and emotional brutality or inhumanity. Thus, she portrays these aspects in her poems. Though this poem does not specify any particular gender, but a whole community of black people. Keeping women in the centre, they had to struggle more because of their gender. It is true that history has the records of the struggle of the black people, their enslavement, oppression, racism, and marginalisation. But the women were doubly marginalized, firstly because of their gender secondly because of their colour, "Maya Angelou through her literary work gave voice to the oppressed African-American women as well as

anyone that feels trapped in a “cage” while she attempted to reveal social problems related to racism, sexism and class segregation.” (Eleftheriou, Eirini, and Katerina.168)

Women Work (Angelou,1978) was written again to address gender equality; how they are confined to domestic works and seen as a machine to give birth to babies, and they are also restricted in legal rights. The title of the poem specifically centres black women and their experiences, describing how society imposed it on their bodies and lives. This poem talks about black women’s work, everything that she has to do which includes household chores that is cleaning, cooking, taking care of children, to harvesting sugar cane and cotton which was referring to both domestic work or errand and slavery that light on the history of enslavement.” The poem *Woman Work* could be a perfect reflection of who Maya Angelou was. She was a woman of many professions. She had to juggle into many a countless profession just to survive and feed her child.” (Cacas, Zoraida, and Saluria.474) In the poem, the speaker itemizes a number of chores which women have to do, consequently which has steeled her time, individuality, and independence. Thus, she appeals to nature for relief, comfort, or solace; she pleads to the sun to shine on her, and rain to fall softly on her. The speaker appeals to the strong storm to blow her away, let her float further up in the sky till she reaches a place where she can rest again.” In the poem, the readers are given the strong impression of an exhausted woman, aged beyond her physical years, while dealing with a tough life and situation within the borders of her slaver’s home and business.” (Cacas, Zoraida, and Saluria. 474) thus, she says that nature is the only thing that truly belongs to her. The speaker finds freedom in nature. It also seems that when the speaker appeals for relief from the nature which she claims that brings her peace and comfort but the readers might also think of final rest, that she wants to leave her body behind and soul in heaven. This poem tells us how women, more particularly black women, are pressured; not only they work traditionally for the home, taking care of the people living, shopping groceries, etc, but also to a slave to pick cotton and cut sugar cane as the poem gives the idea of slavery. The poem “*Women Work*” (Angelou,1978) by Maya Angelou gives a clear picture of traditional household work and enslavement. The poem entails how the world at large avouches black women’s individuality, existence, and independence. They are not allowed to have education, they don’t have the rights to work at their will let alone given political rights or to giving any political suggestion As a result, they have to sacrifice their own needs and desires due to the never-ending demands to meet everyone’s expectations. In the end nothing truly belongs to her, it is only nature that she can call her own.

Where Angelou wrote poems to spread awareness about racism and marginalization, she also wrote to take a stand for oneself, to love and be proud of who you are. In the poem *Phenomenal Woman* (Angelou,1978) the poet, who is also the speaker of the poem, presents herself as an elate and spirited woman. She exclaims to be worthy and confident, irrespective of what others think. Angelou says that a woman should not be insecure about the ridiculous standards set by society; a woman should embrace herself for who she is. The poet discards the societal beauty standards and takes a firm stand that women should have self-confidence and self-acceptance, which is what real beauty is. Maya Angelou portrays how dynamic a woman is not just by how she looks, by but how she is from within. The poet denounces the narrow standards of society that define what beauty is. In the poem the speaker opens with refereeing

to a “secret” that other wants to understand, “Pretty women wonder where my secret lies. I’m not cute or built to suit a fashion model’s size” (Angelou, Line 01-02) she says that she is not cute and is not meant to be like a model, or how beautiful or attractive a woman should look. Angelou particularly targets the fashion industry and the societal beauty standard for setting the obnoxious beauty standards. She affirms that not only does her beauty lie in her physical appearance, but also in who she is, she is confident, proud, and phenomenal. The poet says everyone lingers to get her attention because of her physical appearance, they want to know what it is the thing that makes her look attractive. Even when she reveals they don’t seem to understand, she says that it is not only how she looks physically, though she claims herself to be beautiful in every way but that’s not it. The actual beauty lies in the way she carries herself, it’s her confidence and proud of what she is, who she is, and how she is. If you think of an extraordinary woman, the speaker confidently says that is what she is,” Maya Angelou argues that the sexuality of a woman is not directly related to a pretty face. It’s about what a woman feels within herself.” (Jayageetha and Rani.385) In a way, Angelou also encourages other women to see this in themselves, to accept how they look, to think that they are phenomenal, to have confidence, and to love themselves.

Still I Rise (Angelou,1978) is a poem that openly speaks for the oppressed and marginalized people. It talks about self-respect and confidence. The speaker says she will overcome anything through her confidence and self-esteem. Through this poem, Angelou tries to evoke black people. She says that nothing can stop her from accomplishing things, she is brave, confident, and she can pave her way to achievement. Despite all the dominance and discrimination, she faces or would be facing, she will not let herself down. The speaker rejects racist and negative actions that mark her self-worth, “Generally, the men’s taunts and derogatory comments make the women feel dehumanized. The women have been the subject of mockery and target of men’s witty remarks. They are killed by the men’s hatefulness. So, the women rise to protest against their victimization. While rising from the pain of slavery the woman becomes the hope of all the blacks.” (Apate. 71) This poem is a proclamation of respectability and resilience of marginalized black people. The people continuously try to insult and demean the speaker. To which the speaker says that, they “may” use violence on her, though she does not have the aptness to put a stop to any of this, nevertheless she replies to this treatment not just by keeping her body and soul alive but also to fight back and protect her body and mind and also to raise her voice. The speaker has the capabilities to speak for herself and insists that everyone does the same. She refuses to bend in front of the oppressor. In this poem Angelou says how the white society had marginalized and told everything “lie” and evil, but still, she will withstand it. She says that this “sassiness” “upsets” the oppressors, just because she is confident in all her way. Despite all the hate she receives, she expresses her joy at how she rejected all that negative action, comments, and their desire to see the speaker “broken” both her mind and body. Haters cannot break her self-esteem and confidence, no matter how hard they try to bring her down and insult her. She will continue to live with joy. As the poem title “*Still I Rise*”, she says that despite all the hardships and society filled with hate for her. Where everybody wants to see her broken, not just with her body but also with her soul. She will rise even with all the racist and prejudiced actions she will rise against them.

Angelou conveys that even though there are people who do not wish good for her, the people who want her to get down both physically and mentally. She will resist all this oppression and will rise and grow prosperously, ” Maya Angelou in the poem *Still I Rise* actually tried to express and portrait Black self-attitude against racism by showing the resilience of Black self in America. She revealed various things including socio-political and historical portraits of a society in a certain era.” (Aulia, Rasiah, Putra, and Koso. 03) Black women were expected, or should I say they were under the dominance of societal norms, which didn’t allow them to work, they acted as the puppet in the hands of the white society. Irrespective of colour, women in general were under the domination of a society made by men. They were confined to domestic chores and to give birth, they were not allowed to work let alone to have a voice of their own. Thus, this poem can serve as a feminist manifesto for black women or women of all colours to stand up for themselves.

Mothering Blackness (Angelou,1971) is a part of her semi-autobiography “Just Give Me a Cool Drink of Water Fore I Die.” (Angelou, 1971). This poem shares a small part of her life experience at the time when she was in Ghana. This poem analyses the themes of returning home, an unwavering bond between a mother (motherland) and daughter. The poem is divided into three stanzas, each stanza depicting the characters of the mother and daughter. The first lines are of the daughter who is worried that what she did was wrong, and her mother will not accept her. Later lines of the poem are of the mother who is waiting for the daughter with her warm arms wide open to welcome her. Overall, the tone of the poem is delightful. The meeting of the mother and daughter, realization and accepting the fault of the daughter and the acceptance of her mother gives a sense of harmony to the readers. In the later part of the poem, it is seen that the daughter has slowed her pace. Initially she was rushing home, might be because the fear and anxiety of facing her mother made her “creeping”. On the other hand, the mother seems willing to forgive her. In the last part of the poem, the poet makes a reference to slavery (in a historical context). The daughter “came home blameless” despite what brought her away from home. The poem *Mothering Blackness* marks an honour for the resilience of black women. Even after staying away from home and after returning still their people and the motherland except her with unconditional love. Homecoming symbolises a sense of understanding and belongingness. This poem explores the historical struggles of black people especially women.

The title, “*Rhythms of Resistance: Intersectional Feminism in Maya Angelou’s Poetic Voice*” is appropriate as this paper talks about the black struggle keeping women in the centre through the poems of Angelou as her works beautifully express the history of social status and struggle of black people and how her work empowers them to raise their voices.

“*Rhythms of Resistance*” put forward the idea of oppression in a rhythmic manner. Angelou gives the reader a fuller picture of racism, sexism, discrimination, injustice, and socio-economic inequalities. “Rhythms” literary means putting in place of sound in music. Derived from a Greek word, *rhythmos* which means to flow, which is also found in other forms of arts such as poetry, painting, etc. here rhythms express the idea of resistance. Resistance of black people movements against oppression. This coordinates with Maya Angelou’s writings, which

have the rhythmic quality that not only reflects her life experiences as a black woman but also shows the traces of oppression and resistance against it. "Angelou's poems can be used as a means of learning to instill the value of tolerance, especially in respecting the identity of other nations and not degrading anyone for any reason as every human being has the same rights to live and be independent." (Widjayanti. 147) Thus poetry is not just a form of expressing ideas or feelings, but also an aid for social change and resistance. "*Rhythms of Resistance*" can also be understood as a poetic form of resistance. Her poems reflect her rhythmically. Her works, such as "Caged Bird" (Angelou, 1983), "Still I Rise" (Angelou, 1978), describe the black people's lost freedom and struggles, yet they strive for the unknown, which tells us that no matter how much they suppress them or look down upon still they will rise with confidence. The poet herself has faced the hardships of oppression as she overcomes and defends herself. The poems she writes became a form of resistance against the forces that keep black women from their freedom, justice, and equality. The act of narration can be taken as a form of resistance. The poet's resolution to stand up and be counted in a society that seeks to be silent and rub out black women is both an act to defend themselves and reclamation of force. Angelou's poems and other works speaks up as the declaration to give black women rights to raise their voice, and freedom. Angelou's voice serves as a remodelling of black women's identity and dignity, resistance against marginalization. As "Her powerful words echo her resistance and defiance, leaving a profound impact and legacy. It is through understanding Angelou's work, one can realize the potential of poetry to challenge the status quo, voice dissent, and spur change. Her work reminds us that poetry can, indeed, be a potent instrument of protest." (Sadaf and Rahman. 90)

Intersectionality is described as the different forms of social categories such as caste, colour, race, or gender intersecting or overlapping with each other and causing social conflict, struggle, and discrimination. Intersectional when braided with feminism, it gives a different concept where black women face racism or other forms of oppression. Angelou's poems unveil such traumatic events and experiences also expressing the power of self-confidence, resilience, self-determination, unconditional love, and healing. Her work makes a great contribution to the field of intersectional feminism. Angelou is a notable poet because she has to live the brutal experience as a black woman, she not only addressed her life struggle and history of enslavement but also conveyed themes of self-respect, importance, dignity, confidence, freedom and search for individuality or uniqueness." Feminist intersectionality is a fairly new concept in feminism, race, and sexuality disciplines in European countries, America, and the broader sociological disciplines. This approach provides a theoretical framework and a perceptual sensitivity to the intertwined nature of social dominance dynamics. It endeavors to recognize the interrelationships between many dimensions of oppression, such as racial discrimination, class intolerance, patriarchy, and sexism." (Esmaeel and Saeed. 710) Angelou's poems voice the intricacy of gender and race, repeatedly highlighting intersectional struggles. The poet defends against racism and gender discrimination. Her work not only becomes the voice for resistance but also defies the suppression of society upon black women. In this paper *Rhythms of Resistance*, Angelou's poems are implied as metaphors as it focuses on the marginalized women who have long faced intersectional oppressions. Her writings work as a

means of empowerment for all the women who have had to face the vicious face of society. She highlights the importance of self-confidence, self-love, defying what society expects from women, she also encourages not to limit one's potential. Angelou through her poems celebrates black womanhood, rejecting societal standards and a source of encouragement.

Intersectional Feminism attempts to understand how different forms of social discrimination or inequality intersect, due to which each person has their own experience of oppression. African-American women in particular are twice marginalized. Angelou elaborates on such feminist idea in most of her writings where she not only highlights on the history of enslavement, but also puts forward the personal or another black woman's experiences and evils societal norms; be it their demand to work as a slave or meet the obnoxious beauty standards, Angelou motivates to break out from the cage, fight for dignity, to raise voice against the societal norms, to love yourself for however and whoever you are, to build inner strength and confidence.

The title *Rhythms of Resistance: Intersectional Feminism in the Voice of Maya Angelou* is justified as it illustrates Maya Angelou's personal life and experiences and also incorporates intersectional feminism. Her writings, particularly the poems, braid with the hostilities of social oppression such as marginalization, racism, sexism, and gender. Her words have the powerful rhythms that inspire to speak, resist, and rise. Maya Angelou is not only a writer but also an activist, participating in the Civil Rights Movement, fought for racial equality, freedom, and the rights of women. The resistance against the intersecting societal oppression, viewing it through a feminist lens that criticises racist and gendered structures and the unyielding voice of the writer who represents both personal and societal confrontation. The rhythms of her voice rise against oppression or resistance against what oppresses her with the determination that black woman's voice must be heard. The intersectional feminist lens in Angelou's work does not only speak about the struggle of black women but also serves as a ray of light, hope, empowerment, and encouragement. *The title Rhythms of Resistance* tells us about the struggle to resist against the oppressor, while *Intersectional Feminism* emphasises the intersection of social categories like gender, race, colour, etc. faced by African-American women. Maya Angelou's works play a key role in understanding this aspect of black women's resistance.

I can say that the aim of the present paper is proved, which was to situate Maya Angelou's poems within the theoretical consideration of Intersectional Feminism to explore the conditions of black women and how her writings healed and empowered them. Her work also focuses on uplifting marginalized women. The present also describes the hardships faced as a woman more so as a black woman. How they are unacknowledged and unrecognized. Maya Angelou was the voice for black women who wrote about black womanhood and how she actively wrote and spoke on anti-black racism as a feminist. Overall, Maya Angelou was successful in spreading the message of the unjust society and culture for a black woman through her poems, prose, and other literary works. She talked about the importance of female identity and that they should raise their voice, not tolerating any injustice, any dominance and fight for justice, freedom, and equality. Her poems are the clear markers highlighting Intersectional Feminism, through stereotypes, social conventions, and norms that cannot stop a woman from

achieving her identity. They are not an object to toy with however they feel like, they are not a subject to keep however they want, a woman is an individual who has an identity of their own who can live, write, speak, eat, and wear clothes however they want to. They will not suffer any pain and discrimination. Maya Angelou played the role of the light bearer, spreading the light of hope, encouraging them to resist against the oppression, motivating black women to stand for themselves. Angelou's writings also show the life struggle, enslavement, and social and economic status of black women.

Angelou's poetic voice reflects on the background of intersectional feminism, contributing to the evidence of the overlapping of social categories such as race, colour, gender, class, etc, struggle to fight for justice, equality, and freedom. Through her works, be it poems, prose, or autobiographies, she raises against marginalisation, paves the way for resistance and highlights the oppression of the society faced by black women. Her poems, such as *Caged Bird* and *Still I Rise* give the reader a fuller picture of traumatic experiences faced by black women and their will to fight in any oppressive circumstances and seek their true rights and freedom. Her poems such as *Phenomenal Women* and *Mothering Blackness* highlights on self-respect and confidence beauty is what they are and who they are which does not require to meet the beauty standards set by the society, whereas the later expresses its view of a daughter who worried that she has done something wrong which her mother wont except but her mother is waiting for her with her arms wide open to hug her and welcomes her with unconditional love it seems as the character of the mother is the portrayal of her motherland. Lastly, the poem *Women Work* projects the life's struggle and hardship of a black woman, where she has to work at home to meet the daily household requirements and also work as a slave, she pleads to nature to give her peace and solace. While embracing her experiences, Angelou not only speaks to black women but to all those who were subjected to stereotypes and injustice, marginalization, and other forms of oppression, she urges them to achieve enough strength to resist. Angelou's power of words influences the feminist movement that focuses on the significance of recognising and acknowledging the interconnection of various forms of oppression.

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